

FRACTURE MECHANICS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES IN CRYOTANK ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In order to reduce the operating cost of new reusable launch vehicles (RLV's), recent interest has focused on reduction of structural weight. For single stage to orbit (SSTO) vehicles with internal propellant tanks (cryotanks), significant weight savings is possible with the use of polymer matrix composite material construction when compared to metallic construction. Due to the severe environments encountered by cryotanks – liquid hydrogen temperatures upon pre-launch to elevated temperatures upon re-entry – candidate materials for this application must be characterized in simulated environments to ensure design reliability.

In this work, adhesively bonded joints with composite adherends are evaluated both experimentally and analytically in environments similar to those encountered in cryotanks. Adherends are of unidirectional graphite-BMI construction, bonded with AF-191M film adhesive. Monotonic mode I adhesive fracture toughness tests are performed at near liquid nitrogen temperature (-190°C), room temperature (27°C) and elevated temperatures (121°C, 177°C) to determine temperature effects on critical strain energy release rate. Experimental results exhibit reduced adhesive fracture toughness at temperatures other than room temperature. Elevated temperatures are noted to have a more profound effect on adhesive fracture toughness than cryogenic temperature. Experimental tests are modeled analytically using FRANC-2D finite element software. Mechanistic effects of residual thermal stresses and their role in affecting measured critical strain energy release rate are evaluated.

Key Terms: adhesive joints, polymer matrix composites (PMC's), debonding, fracture toughness, residual stress

INTRODUCTION

As the cost of space operations increases, new designs for reusable launch vehicles (RLV's) have come to light as a necessary solution for future space missions. Several candidate designs have materialized, to some degree, in an effort to not only prove out the success of a given RLV design, but also to test and demonstrate the state of technologies used in the construction. Two of these designs, the DC-XA and X-33 RLV technology demonstrators, are noted for their use of advanced materials technology to accomplish goals of reduced operating cost by decreasing vehicle weight.

For most single-stage-to-orbit (SSTO) designs, propellant storage tanks are often the largest component of the vehicle. Therefore, it is probable that for most designs, weight reduction of the propellant tanks will cause a significant reduction in total vehicle weight. To achieve this, polymer matrix composite (PMC) materials – with their increased specific strength and stiffness (when compared to traditional aerospace alloys) – have come to light as a candidate material technology for RLV propellant tanks. To provide a perspective of the possible weight

savings, the DC-XA propellant tank, constructed of PMC materials (graphite/epoxy) is noted as being 544 kg (1200 lbs) lighter than the similar aluminum tank of the DC-X¹.

Liquid hydrogen and liquid oxygen are often typical propellants for RLV propulsion systems. Since these elements have a boiling point of -253°C and -183°C respectively, the materials used in the construction of the propellant storage tanks must sustain applied loads while immersed in the cryogenic environment. (Due to this cryogenic environment, these tanks are often referred to as cryotanks; this terminology will be adopted hereinafter.) In addition to this adverse cryogenic environment, RLV cryotank structures are also subjected to elevated temperature environments upon entry of the vehicle into the earth's atmosphere. To correctly determine the viability of using PMC's in the design of RLV cryotanks, it is essential that these candidate materials be accurately characterized in simulated cryotank environments.

In the implementation of PMC materials in primary structure, it is well established that the method of adhesive bonding is a highly beneficial, albeit hesitated, method of joining components. The benefits of weight savings and reduced manufacturing time, when compared to traditional mechanically fastening methods, are often shadowed by the high dependence of bond integrity on process quality. In order to reap the full weight-reducing benefits of PMC materials in cryotank structures, it is essential that adhesively bonded joints be used as the primary means of component attachment wherever possible.

It is well known that PMC's and adhesively bonded joints have been used successfully in the commercial and military aircraft industries. Although less well known, PMC's have also been viewed as candidate materials for superconductor applications. This use and interest has brought about significant research into the mechanical behavior of PMC's in simulated aircraft and cryogenic environments. In much of the aircraft-based research and less so in the cryogenic field, investigations have been performed into the fracture mechanics response of PMC's and adhesively bonded joints in the appropriate environment. Essential to determining the reliability of using PMC materials and adhesively bonded joints in new RLV cryotank applications, the fracture mechanics approach is used here to determine the viability of using a particular PMC/adhesively bonded joint system through coupon mode I adhesive fracture toughness tests. In addition, a finite element model of the test coupon is constructed and analyzed to determine what mechanisms may influence the performance of this (and other) PMC/adhesively bonded systems.

RESEARCH APPROACH

The fundamental basis of this work is to investigate the durability of PMC materials and their assemblies in a simulated cryotank environment. For a particular focus, experimental fracture mechanics is used to investigate the behavior of a particular PMC assembly, while analytical fracture mechanics methods are used to investigate the particular system for general trends that may apply to other PMC systems as well. Specifically, adhesively bonded PMC coupons are experimentally tested to determine mode I adhesive fracture toughness, obtained by determining the critical strain energy release rate necessary for crack propagation. The tests are performed at four temperatures ranging from cryogenic to elevated, to simulate temperatures endured by cryotank structures. These coupons are then modeled using finite element software, and the effects of temperature change on strain energy release rate are examined.

EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

To determine the performance of a candidate PMC bonded joint system, double cantilever beam (DCB) adhesively bonded PMC specimens were constructed. The adherends were constructed of IM7/5250-4 graphite/bismaleimide unidirectional prepreg. The balanced and symmetric adherend laminates were each constructed of 10 plies, with a layup sequence of $[0^{\circ}_4/90^{\circ}]_s$, orienting the 0° plies in the direction of specimen length. The adherends were cured using an autoclave, resulting in a cured adherend thickness of 1.30mm. The adhesive used to join the adherends was AF-191M modified epoxy adhesive, cured at 177°C as recommended by the manufacturer. The selected adhesive contained a scrim cloth to maintain a cured bondline thickness of $250\mu\text{m}$.

ASTM standard D5528² (mode I interlaminar fracture toughness) was used as a guide for DCB specimen construction and geometry. ASTM D5528 was used in lieu of ASTM D5041³ since it is more refined in the areas of data reduction and specimen geometries. The geometry of the DCB specimen is displayed in Figure 1. To introduce an initial unbonded flaw region, a halohydrocarbon release film strip was inserted at one end of the specimen during fabrication of the adhesive bond. Load introduction was accomplished through the use of aluminum loading blocks, drilled for load train attachment through a clevis and pin arrangement. The loading blocks were adhesively attached to the PMC adherends for the room and elevated temperature experiments. For the cryogenic experiments, the loading blocks were mechanically attached to the adherends with fasteners.

Figure 1: Double cantilever beam specimen geometry.

To determine performance of the selected system in a simulated cryotank environment, the specimens were tested in four temperature environments. Cryogenic temperatures of -190°C were applied through immersion of the specimen in liquid nitrogen. Tests were performed at 27°C to establish an ambient baseline. In addition, tests were performed at elevated temperatures of 121°C and 177°C . These temperatures were selected to simulate cryotank full fuel launch, ambient storage conditions, and high speed atmospheric entry respectively. To ensure steady-state thermal conditions, the specimens were subjected to the appropriate environment 10 minutes prior to testing. Elevated temperature conditions were achieved through use of a recirculating oven. The more challenging cryogenic conditions were obtained through an innovative chamber design noted in Figure 2. The chamber accommodated the cryogenic tests by allowing immersion of the specimen in liquid nitrogen. In addition, the chamber design allowed for the use of intermittent crack length monitoring as well as the recycling of liquid nitrogen after testing.

Figure 2: Liquid nitrogen environment chamber.

Tests were performed in displacement control, at a rate of 1.9 mm/min. Raw data values of load and crosshead displacement were obtained from each of the tests. Specimen crack length was measured visually. To determine the adhesive fracture toughness of the system, the critical mode I strain energy release rate for crack propagation (G_{IC}) was determined. The onset of crack propagation was determined by deviation from linearity of the load-displacement trace, noted as the deviation from linearity method (NL) in ASTM D5528. At the point of deviation, critical values of load and displacement were obtained. The modified beam theory (MBT) method of ASTM D5528 was used to calculate G_{IC} from specimen measurements of width (B) and crack length (a) in addition to critical values of load (P_C) and displacement (δ_C) obtained during the tests. As recommended by the standard, correction factors of Δ , F and N were used to correct for crack root effects (elastic foundation, root rotation), large displacements and loading block rotations respectively⁴, to arrive at a modified MBT equation for G_{IC} :

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P_C\delta_C}{2B(a + \Delta)} \cdot \left(\frac{F}{N}\right)$$

ANALYTICAL MODEL

The experimental tests described above provide a quantitative performance measure of a specific PMC bonded joint system. As is the case with PMC materials and their bonded joints, a change in constituents often elicits a significant change in overall behavior. Since this change can be done with relative ease, especially for polymer matrices and adhesives, it is noted that vast resources would be required to perform an experimental investigation of every PMC adhesively bonded joint system to determine viable candidates for cryotank applications. Therefore, an identification of general, qualitative trends in cryogenic PMC adhesively bonded joint behavior may aid in efficiently determining a candidate system.

As is typically the case in adhesively bonded joints, and even more so in joints with graphite fiber reinforced PMC adherends, the adherends have a considerably lower longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) than the polymeric adhesive used to join them. Due to this CTE mismatch significant residual stresses will develop in the system upon cooling or

heating of the assembly from the stress-free temperature. In the case of adhesively bonded joints (with $CTE_{\text{adhesive}} > CTE_{\text{adherend}}$) subjected to cryogenic temperatures far below elevated curing temperatures, residual in-plane tensile stresses will result in the adhesive layer accompanied by residual in-plane compressive stresses in the adherends. Since the adhesive layer is typically weaker in axial strength than the joined adherends this result is unfavorable – from a strength-based perspective. From a fracture mechanics perspective, this may or may not be the case.

For a bonded joint DCB specimen in mode I loading, the residual stresses induced by the reduction in temperature will cause an inward deflection of the free (through cracked) ends as displayed in Figure 3. This will have an effect on the state of stress at the crack tip, the result visualized by noting that this deflection of the DCB tips moves the applied load through a distance, changing the energy state of the system and therefore the strain energy release rate (G). Nairn^{5,6} has developed the closed form solution for this change in G , and notes that this may affect the results of adhesive fracture toughness tests.

Figure 3: Effect of residual stresses on the studied mode I DCB specimen.

To develop an understanding of the effect of these residual stresses, an analytical model of the experimental bonded joint specimen was constructed and analyzed. The mechanistic effects of a cryogenic environment on specimen behavior were qualitatively examined by determining the effects of an applied temperature reduction on the strain energy rate. FRANC-2D finite element analysis software⁷ was used for this analysis, specifically for its triangular elements exhibiting an $r^{-1/2}$ singularity. The material properties used in the model are from Pagano et al.⁸ and Butkus et al.⁹, and are noted in Table 1.

Several assumptions were made in the construction of this FEA model that limit the accuracy of the model, yet allow for investigation of general, qualitative trends. In the model the adhesive was modeled as a linearly elastic isotropic continuum; the adherends as an orthotropic, linearly elastic continuum. The crack tip was modeled in the midplane of the adhesive layer, and linear elastic fracture mechanics was assumed to apply. Both the adhesive and adherends were assumed to undergo no irreversible or time-dependent deformation. Both were also assumed to exhibit constant material properties over the range of temperatures examined.

Adherend (IM7/5250-4 laminate)		Adhesive (AF-191M)	
E ₁₁	138.0 GPa	E	1.534 GPa
E ₂₂	46.0 GPa	ν	0.42
E ₃₃	10.3 GPa	α	$67.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
ν_{12}	0.16		
ν_{13}	0.50		
ν_{23}	0.55		
G ₁₂	5.80 GPa		
α_{11}	$1.65 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$		
α_{22}	$7.47 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$		
E = Young's Modulus		11 = Laminate plane fiber direction	
ν = Poisson's Ratio		22 = Laminate plane transverse direction	
G = Shear Modulus		33 = out of laminate plane direction	
α = Coefficient of Thermal Expansion			

Table 1: Material properties used in finite element analyses.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

From the experimental tests, values of mode I adhesive fracture toughness were obtained at temperatures ranging from cryogenic to elevated. These results are summarized in Table 2 and Figure 4. Mean values of adhesive fracture toughness are reported along with the standard deviation for each data set at the prescribed temperature. It is noted that only propagation fracture toughness values are reported here – values of initiation fracture toughness, which are often dependent upon initial flaw material and geometry, are not presented. From these results it is apparent that temperatures other than room negatively affect the mode I fracture toughness of the IM7/5250-4 – AF-191M adhesively bonded joint system. As the glass transition temperature (T_g) is approached, it is noted that high temperature has a greater effect than cryogenic temperature; a reduction of 85% and 60% respectively.

Mode I Adhesive Fracture Toughness - Experimental Results			
Propagation values only - Initiation values excluded			
Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Mean G_{IC} (J/m^2)	Std. Dev. (J/m^2)	# of Data Points
-190	697.96	165.23	7
27	1657.30	179.22	14
121	526.81	81.80	3
177	240.22	53.20	2

Table 2: Experimental results – mode I adhesive fracture toughness.

Figure 4: Trends in adhesive fracture toughness with temperature.

To provide insight into the behavior of crack propagation through the specimen length, the crack growth resistance curve, or R-curve, is examined. Figure 5 presents the R-curve results at ambient and cryogenic temperatures. From the trends it is noted that at room temperature, an apparent toughening is observed with further crack propagation. In contrast, the cryogenic temperature trends display a decrease in fracture toughness, which is uncommon, and may be a result of residual stresses and their effects on the crack tip stress state.

Figure 5: Crack growth resistance curves at ambient and cryogenic temperature.

Finally, the fracture surfaces of the specimen were examined to determine fracture mode. The fracture surfaces of representative specimen tested at cryogenic, ambient and elevated temperature are presented in Figure 6. It was determined that at room temperature, cohesive failure was exhibited. This result is labeled as cohesive since it occurred in the midplane of the adhesive, although it is technically an adhesive failure, since the fracture occurred at the interface between the scrim cloth and the adhesive. At the elevated temperature, adhesive failure consistently occurred between the adhesive and one of the PMC adherends. The cryogenic fracture surfaces, however, exhibited mixed adhesive/cohesive failure. The crack propagated in a meandering fashion, propagating along the adherend/adhesive interface for a short distance, then through the adhesive layer at an angle near 90° to the surface until encountering the opposing adherend/adhesive interface. The crack then propagated a short distance before turning back through the adhesive layer to the original surface, and continued in this manner, leaving a hackled appearance. This occurred almost instantaneously, as the crack grew in a stick-slip fashion at this temperature, in contrast to the stable, crosshead-controlled crack growth exhibited at ambient and elevated temperatures.

Figure 6: Adhesive fracture surfaces at various temperatures.

ANALYTICAL RESULTS

The constructed finite element model was analyzed to determine qualitative trends that may apply to adhesively bonded PMC joints in general. As discussed, it was determined that thermally induced residual stresses due to CTE mismatch may have an effect on the state of stress at the crack tip. To determine the extent of this effect, an arbitrary crack length was chosen, and held fixed. External mode I loading was applied to the model to obtain an arbitrary strain energy release rate (1000 J/m^2) without the effect of residual stresses. The value of applied load then established a base value. Then, to determine the effect of the residual stresses, a negative temperature change was incrementally applied to the model. At each temperature increment, the applied load value was adjusted to exhibit the same strain energy release rate of 1000 J/m^2 . This was continued up to a temperature change of -375°C , representing the temperature shift between cure (177°C) and liquid nitrogen. The result is then presented in a plot of temperature shift vs. applied load for a constant strain energy release rate, presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Effect of CTE mismatch between adhesive and adherends.

As noted by the figure, as the temperature is reduced, an increase in applied load is necessary to maintain a constant level of strain energy release rate – a favorable effect. Therefore, according to the model, it can be deduced that for adhesively bonded joints in general, when constructed of adherends and adhesive exhibiting a CTE mismatch, a reduction in temperature has a definite effect on the crack tip stress state – a favorable effect in the case of $\text{CTE}_{\text{adhesive}} > \text{CTE}_{\text{adherend}}$. For the opposite case, it is noted that a negative, unfavorable effect is probable.

CONCLUSIONS

As PMC materials are being considered for primary structure in cryotank applications, it is imperative to determine the behavior of these materials in the appropriate environment. More specifically, the fracture mechanics behavior of candidate materials is essential to ensure design reliability.

In this work, a candidate adhesively bonded PMC joint system was tested to determine mode I adhesive fracture toughness in simulated cryotank environments. It was determined that temperatures other than room negatively affected the fracture toughness of the selected IM7/5250-4 – AF-191M system, with elevated temperatures having more of an effect than cryogenic temperature. Examination of the crack growth R-curves noted an apparent toughening effect in ambient temperature tests, while cryogenic results noted an unusual effect of a decreased fracture toughness with crack propagation. Investigation of fracture surfaces noted a cohesive

failure at room temperature, adhesive failure at elevated temperature, and a hackled, mixed cohesive/adhesive failure at cryogenic temperature.

A FRANC-2D finite element model of the experimental DCB specimen was constructed and analyzed to determine qualitative trends in adhesively bonded joints subjected to a cryogenic environment. Due to a significant CTE mismatch between the adherends and adhesive of the joint, residual stresses develop within the adhesive layer that may affect the crack tip stress state. Results of the FEA model show that this does occur, and for the case of adhesively bonded joints with $CTE_{\text{adhesive}} > CTE_{\text{adherend}}$ subjected to a reduction in temperature, the resulting residual stresses have a positive, favorable effect on the crack tip stress state. This effect is shown qualitatively as a necessary increase in applied load to maintain a constant strain energy release rate as the temperature is reduced.

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